

The Philosophical Thoughts of Mathematics Education: Their Inputs in the Classroom

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Abstract

The article ‘The Philosophical thoughts of Mathematics Education: their inputs in the classroom’ has its focus of discussion on the following philosophical thoughts as it affects mathematics education. And these are realism, naturalism, pragmatism, existentialism, humanism, Logicism, formalism and intuitionism. The article ends up with conclusion.

Keywords: Philosophical thoughts, Mathematics Education, inputs, classroom.

Introduction: The Universe is a composition of thoughts and these thoughts do oscillate in the minds of men. These oscillatory movements occur in every man per second. But these thoughts most times vary from man to man and within an individual too. As long as the world has existed, there is no thought that has received hundred percentage acceptance, not even the thought of the Creator of the Universe, whose secrecy is yet to be discovered by man. Man who is being studied in totality by philosophers is such a complex being that Beck, (1979) in Okoto, (1998) cited Jean-Paul Sartre, a French Existentialist Philosopher, saying “man puts his own very being into question”. Perhaps it was on that note Bebebiafai (2006:3), sees philosophy as an attitude towards life and a love of wisdom that makes life to become meaningful and purposeful by clarifying, justifying and verifying issues through man’s eroticism of concepts and principles. It must have been through this perception that the Biblical Philosophers came up with the saying, “a world without end”.

Wokocha (2005:7) opined that language of instruction has to be properly analyzed for clarity, the policies also have to be spared from ambiguities, which are the realms of philosophy; and that no meaningful curriculum planning and development can materialize without a philosophical foundation. He therefore admonished curriculum developers to be conversant with the various relevant modes of philosophical enquiry.

It must have been on this premise these thoughts of man, though interwoven, are been classified, so as to narrow down or shorten the radius of the vicious circle. And one of these classes is the school of mathematics, whose radius of its vicious circle value still has infinity. Many works have been carried out under mathematics yet man has not gotten to the centre of the circle, not to talk of realizing the diametrical dimension.

All the same, man has continued to explore the wisdom of the Universe, properly looking for what he feels is the true situation of an event. And at the end of his exploration, he may found joy in seeing the event, the way he feels it should have been. After two to three years, if not less, others might come out with a different view of the same event and sometimes the founder himself will

see some contradictions or improvement on what he has discovered. This has been the mystery, the philosophers are working around the clock to clarify, justify and verify for man to see the world in various perceptions, (Bebibiafai, 2006).

It is on this same trend, man with his philosophical eyes has gone into divisionalizing mathematics into compartments and one of these compartments is the “Philosophy of Mathematics” which this paper is been focused on. Its discussion will, therefore be based on the following schools of philosophical thoughts;

The Philosophical Thoughts

Philosophical thinking is all about pursuing knowledge, search for the truth into understanding our own values and standing to evaluate, criticize and defend these same values that are peculiar to what the society holds. (Nagwa,2024).On the strength of this holding the search for knowledge had given birth to the following philosophical thoughts that have something relevance to the teaching and learning of Mathematics Education. And these philosophical thoughts include: realism, naturalism, pragmatism, existentialism, humanism, Logicism, formalism and intuitionism. They will be discussed side by side with mathematics education to show how their thinking contributes to the teaching and learning of the subject mathematics.

Realism and Mathematics Education: Realism is a brain child of Aristotle and its philosophers believe that the reality that people know exist independently of the mind. Realists said tress, birds, rivers, water, animals, stars, air, etc are not images formed from mind perceptions; and they are real entities that occupy the entire universe; which only correspond to the objects of sensory perceptions. It is from these entities, the mind perception was able to form other objects by adding one and two (e.g. water and salt) or discovers that a single entity has two components (e.g. H₂O form water). Each of these Philosophical units will be viewed in line with mathematics education. It is on this basis Locke (1632-1704) in Encyclopedia Britannica, (2024) rejected the notion of the existence of innate ideas, which conditioned or structured man’s perception of the world. He rather asserted that man when he was born as a child; his mind was like a blank sheet of paper, which he puts in his language as “tabular rasa”. And that these entities that occupy the universe will start writing on that blank mind through the five sensory organs. Good examples are, the sound of a bird, through the ear; the shape of a tree, through the eyes and so on.

Naturalism and Mathematics Education: Naturalists believe that anything existing on this earth can be explained satisfactorily by using natural or scientific terms (IEP,2024). This believes was so on the ground that, nature was seen as a sum total of objects, space and item. And whatever happens on earth has a link with these three terms. Greek philosopher, Thales who is seen as the originator of Naturalism stated in the 6th century B.C that the key to the knowledge of Ultimate reality is Naturalism,(Antonis, 2021) .

Going by this school of thought one can recall this biblical statement of **Thomas**, that said “seeing is believing”. And to be kind did, what one sees and hears last longer in the memory than what one hears and not seen. Mathematical Education teachers should make good use of this school of thought by showing natural objects like the stem of a palm or coconut tree as an example while teaching are of sphere. These topics taught through these media will last longer in the memory of

the learner than drawing them on the chalk board, which may not let the learner to see the features very well.

Pragmatism and Mathematics Education: These groups of Philosophers believe in solving an existing problem through practical approach rather than using theoretical or idealistic consideration. They do not believe in absolutism and dogmas of idealism and realism. They see their school as a philosophy of action which emphasized the use of practical in settling pragmatic ideas and techniques derived from science, science method, democracy and experiences. Charles Pierce was the formulator of the name Pragmatism while William James used the policy to settle a metaphysical problem that seems to be endless; it later became a touchstone to measure validity of any notion. Hence it is considered as experimentation, empiricism, instrumentalism, progressive, means and not ends.

Mathematics like any other science course has a practical approach. But most items the Educators fail to use the practical approach to problems presented in numbers or numerical forms. For example in teaching volume, for the teacher to involve the students in measuring out the length, breadth and height of the object, before applying the formula, he goes straight to the board and copy out values for length, breadth and height (for an unseen object) and starts calculating. This approach or methodology will not make the class as lively as the practical approach that will involve every learner in getting his or her own measurement before computation. Mathematics Educators are therefore advised to use the pragmatism approach in the class so as to carry everybody along.

Existentialism and Mathematics Education: Here Existentialist sees man as the creator of all ideas. He is taken as the subject and not the object, and to them he owes nothing to nature except his existence. They believe that man is independent of God and society. They see the physical world as irrational, meaningless and purposeless and that, it is man who explores his feelings, emotions, hopes, desires and physical passions and keeps the world going. They believe on questions like “who am I?” “Why am I here?” “Where am I going”, “What should I do?” and “What should I believe in?” This Philosophical thought deals more on the area of the learner. The question raise above as applied to man, are the very questions each learner supposed to be asking himself daily, for him to be self actualized. This is because questions are asked for answers to be supplied.

Looking at the above situation if applied to mathematics teaching in the class, students suppose to be asking themselves, why am I here?, where am I going after now? and what should I do them? In answering these questions any serious minded students will sit up because they will need this subject (mathematics) in their higher institutions studies, if they are secondary school students or in the application of daily activities, if they are graduates of higher Institutions or Primary or Secondary School Certificate holders, who have decided to work with their certificates at that level. it is therefore mandatory for the Mathematic Education to infuse this knowledge into their students for them to be self actualized while in the school.

Humanism and Mathematics Education: Humanism is man centered, which opposes medieval, values, ideals, thoughts and cosmology. They believe that man is a social animal who must live

freely and intelligently and that the society he lives as created by himself for himself and not by other being. They see human being as the standard in measuring every other thing and not theism (superman) or mechanism (subhuman) as others believe.

In looking at this believe in line with mathematics Education, it reveals that mathematics learning is learner's centered. The teacher to the humanists is of no serious important as far as their believe is concerned. He will only function as one of the structure of the cosmos, which he uses in making the components of the society he creates for himself. Mathematics Educators should therefore develop this humanist thought in the minds of the learners. The moment they (the learners) come to realize that it is only them that can decide what is good for them; a greater part of the mathematical problems is solved.

Logicism and Mathematics Education: Gottlob Frege the founder of logicism, talked about the nature of Mathematical truth. He claimed that Mathematics is logic because he was able to build up arithmetic from a system of logic with a general principle of comprehension, which he called Basic Law V, (IEP-Frege, 2024). But later other logicists came up and flawed Frege's concept. Those among them were Russell and Whitehead. Their claim (Particularly Russell) was that the Basic Law V, is inconsistent. They therefore went into build up much of modern mathematics into the logicism, which eventually changed the claim of deriving mathematics from the pure logic, (Speaks, 2007).

For example the inclusion of axiom of reducibility, which Russell, claimed has nothing to do with logic. They therefore called their approach analytical. Others equally argued that all of mathematics was not reduced to elementary logic but they did reduce Mathematics elementary logic. Carnap (1931), presented Logicism thesis in two forms. He said:

1. The concepts of mathematics can be derived from logical concepts through explicit definitions.
2. The theorems of mathematics can be derived from logical axioms through purely logical deduction.

That he also tend to repudiate the fact that all mathematics has be reduced to logic. This assertion must have been made at the time mathematics was of music, astronomy and arithmetic. Considering the everyday mathematic alone as part of modern mathematics; one finds out that there are some clear truth in mathematics that are not logic based. The paradigm of it is the case of buying and selling. If one biro costs N5, 000 the cost of ten biros will be N50, 000; no logical statement attached.

Formalism and Mathematics Education: Formalist holds that mathematical statements are about consequences of certain strings guided with manipulative rules. And that such strings (like axioms, rules of inference, etc) will only hold or become consistent or generate other strings corresponding to the existing one; if a meaning assigned to it doesn't prove the worth of the string wrong or become inconsistent; but when the rules of the same strings become inconsistent, then the statement becomes untrue. It is on this premise formalist sees the strings in mathematics as not being absolute true but a relative one. Hilbert argued that if mathematics is to be independents of

suspicious empirical assumptions, it must be free from assertions concerning the existence of infinite structures that are not physically considerable. He therefore muted a program that intends to be a complete and consistent axiomatization of all of mathematics i.e. a derivative that is free of contradictions.

He needed to prove the consistency of mathematical axiomatization from the assumption that the “finitary arithmetic” was consistent but Godel’s incompleteness theorems disproved it. It states that sufficiently expressive consistent axiom system would contain the finitary arithmetic as a subsystem. Thus, the fact that no contradictions can be derived from the system is untrue. In order to show that any axiomatic system of mathematics is consistent, one need to first assume the consistency of a system of mathematics that is in a sense stronger than the system to be proven consistent. Here formalist upholds the theory of working from the known to the unknown.

Intuitionism and Mathematics Education: This school of philosophy holds that there are no non-experienced mathematical truths on infinite structure. This school of thought was founded by Brouwer in response to his objection of the formalized logic of any sort for mathematics. Brouwer and his cohort had two sorts of doubts about the infinite structure. They doubt the consistency of a set of statements describing an infinite structure and also doubting the assumption that there is a well-defined standard model for infinite structure.

There defense on the first case was that an infinite sequence can only work on zero and one numbers, where it can be proved true or false if refuted. But any number beyond one can neither be proved true nor false, hence are the statements describing an infinite structure not consistent as it affects number theory.

The mathematics teacher should note the tabular Rasa realism of Locke while in the classroom; It is obvious that the mind is blank from birth; if it were not mathematics topics being taught wouldn’t have been looked abstract. There wouldn’t have been any statement like “I don’t understand”. Most items when a placement test is given to the learners, several people are scoring zero. This is a clear indication that, that area of their mind is blank. Mathematics teachers should therefore not assume that their students know what they are going to teach them. They should always have the feeling that their minds are blank concerning what they are going to impart onto them. A teacher should not talk about $1 + 2$, when the mind of the learner is still blank on 1 and 2 digits.

Scholars were therefore advised not to assume that they can characterize any finite number of axioms for all the things they would intuitively recognize as correct methods of proof.

There second position argues that if there is a well-define standard model of infinite structure, the axioms should not satisfy only zero or one situations but should be capable of proving all models true within the number theory.

In other words, the intuitionists oppose to the fact that every statement about an infinite totality is either true or false. There defense here stated that if number theory is not a closed concept, then the notion of number theory is surely not mathematically meaningful, Thy therefore advised again that philosophers and other scholars should drop the assumption that there is a well-defined standard model for infinite structure in number theory. They strongly believe that any idea that comes to mind intuitively can be ascertain through proof but since the infinite sequence of numbers

beyond one cannot be proved true or refuted falsely, the idea surrounding the concept is not intuitive.

But if the intuitionist had moved steps further from the point they are concluding, there would have been a solution to their problem. Archimedes wouldn't have shouted "Eureka", (Engelsberg 2021) if his intuition was stopped half way but he got on with the intuitive idea until it was practically proved. Mathematics teachers and students should therefore always pen down their intuitive ideas and work towards the end point where, they will have a proof or a solution to the problem bordering them.

Conclusion

These philosophical thoughts really have a role to play in the teaching and learning processes of mathematics Education in the classroom. The teachers should therefore know that the learner's mind, to an extent is blank and needs filling with the unknown. Teachers should be mindful of this factor anytime they are in the classroom.

On the part of the learners, they should be conscious of the nationalism factor of what one sees and hears last longer in the memory than what he hears and not seen. Use pragmatism approach of believe in solving an existing problem through practical approach rather than using theoretical or idealistic consideration; existentialism believe of questions pattern like "who am I?" "Why am I here?" "Where am I going", "What should I do?" and "What should I believe in?" should not be ignored. In the humanism revelation of mathematics learning as learner's centered, teachers should go deep in finding the mathematical gift that is in the learner. And finally formalism thought of experience and intuitive factors of idea flashing the mind of the learner should be brought out by the teacher because these are also realities that the learner SHOULD be mindful of, in the process of learning mathematics education.

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